

A STUDY ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTY OF GLASS/JUTE INTER-LAMINATE HYBRID FABRIC COMPOSITE

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1 Introduction

Polymer composites were introduced into hundreds of applications from golf clubs and tennis rackets to jet ski, aircraft, missile, spacecraft and marine application. Other usages include transportation, chemical equipment and machinery construction, electrical and electronics appliances, fishing rods and storage tanks[1].

Fibre reinforced polymer composites have potential application in structural and non-structural areas as they have interesting properties such as high specific stiffness and strength, good fatigue performance and damage tolerance, corrosion resistance, low thermal expansion, non-magnetic properties and low energy consumption during fabrication[2-5].

Research on new materials is stimulated by the needs of environmental protection, low costs, easy production and good properties. In last decades, more and more scholars started their research on natural renewable resources, in order to meet those needs, especially to prevent further stress on the environment[6].

Renewable fibers are often considered only for markets that require low costs and high production rates, and can accept low performance. However, these fibers have many properties that would be an advantage in another market, such as light weight, high specific strength compare to glass and carbon, and low energy requirements during processing. Their potential for use in molded articles not needing high strength for acceptable performance has been tried in equipment housings, roofing for low-cost housing, and in large diameter piping[7].

The growing interest in recent years in the use of natural fibers as reinforcing components for thermo plastics and thermosets, was not only for their advantages in environmental protection and low costs, but also for advantages including high specific strength and modulus, low density, renewable nature, biodegradability, absence of associated health hazard, easy fibre surface modification, wide availability and relative non-abrasiveness. The

physical and mechanical properties of natural fibers are mainly depended on their physical composition such as structure of fibers, cellulose content, angle of fibrils, and cross section[3,8].

On the other hand, nature fiber has it inherent drawbacks. As it usually products from organism and has a complicated relation with water. Water absorption has a remarkable effect on it. Many researchers involved in this study which focused on the influence of water/liquid absorption on mechanical property[9,10].

Others devoted themselves to investigate hybrid composites made of nature fiber and glass fiber. Hybrid composites fabricated by banana fibre and glass fibre with varying fibre length and fibre loading was researched by Seena Joseph and M. S. Sreekala[11]. The data of tensile, flexural and impact properties were collected. Three layers hybrid composites of oil palm and jute fibre were also introduced by M. Jawaid and H. P. S. Abdul Khalil [1], and the mechanical resistance, void content and tensile properties were investigated. Kazuya Okubo and Toru Fujii[12] devoted their study in bamboo fibre composites, and tested their mechanical properties. They found out that the bamboo fibers (bundles) had a sufficient specific strength, which is equivalent to that of conventional glass fibers. Moe Moe Thwe and Kin Liao[13] made bamboo-glass fiber reinforced polymer matrix hybrid composite, and its fatigue behavior under cyclic tensile load were studied. P. V. Joseph and G. Mathew[14] studied short sisal fibre reinforced polypropylene composites containing both untreated and treated fibers. Those composites were studied with reference to fibre loading, fibre length, chemical treatments, frequency and temperature. S. C. Amico [15] studied the mechanical properties of glass-sisal hybrid composites. The simple treatment of drying or washing/drying sisal fibers improved the tensile and flexural properties of the sisal composites.

Mohan and Kishore[16] investigated the flexural properties and compressive properties of jute-glass hybrid reinforced epoxy laminates. The effects of

stacking sequence on tensile, flexural and inter-laminar shear properties of woven jute and glass fabric reinforced polyester hybrid composites were investigated by Sabeel Ahmed and Vijayarangan [17]. The study indicated that jute fibres offer same reinforcing effect in a matrix as synthetic fibre. However, their efficiency and level of reinforcement is different. Two kinds of glass-jute fabric were manufactured using a total fibre volume of $50 \pm 2\%$ (14 glass fibre layers + 4 jute fibre layers), and the mechanical properties were tested by Igor M. De Rosa and Carlo Santulli[18]. However, only three-point flexural test was performed by them. Their study confirmed concerns about post-impact residual properties and impact damage effect on E-glass/jute hybrid laminates.

In this study, two kinds of jute-glass hybrid fabric were used to fabricate composite by hand lay-up method. Compared to previous studies, the hybrid fiber was inside the ply. Two structure included [0] and [0/90/0] and different angle were tested to examine the mechanical properties of jute-glass hybrid composites.

2 Materials and Experiment

2.1 Fabrics

Fig. 1. Jute-Glass hybrid fabric structure

Two kinds of jute-glass hybrid fabric were used in this study. Fabric structures were illustrated in figure 1. Both structures were in woven fabric. In the two structures, all jute fibers were distributed in 90° direction with part of glass fibers. In 0° direction, all fibers were glass fibers. There were same jute fiber proportion in those two structures but different arrange method . The fiber arrangement was shown in Figure 1, and the fiber proportion of each fiber was shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Fiber proportion of jute-glass hybrid fabric Gram Weight (g/m²)

	Total	Type A	Type B
0°	Glass Fiber	618	618
	Jute Fiber	229	229
90°	Glass Fiber	133.4	131.353
	Jute Fiber	185.6	187.647

Unsaturated polyester resin (Showa: RIGORAC 150HRBQNTNW) was used as matrix. (Polymer was mixed with the hardener MEKPO (PERMEK N; NOF Corporation) in a ratio of 100:0.7.

2.2 Composite manufacturing

The composite plate was fabricated by hand lay-up method. One ply ([0]) in 0°, 45°, 90° and three plies ([0/90/0]) in 0°, 90° were fabricated respectively. One ply specimens and three plies specimens for tensile test is shown in Figure 2, while one ply specimens and three plies specimens for bending test was shown in Figure 3. After fabrication, the materials were disposed on die for 24 hours for cure. Post cure was followed in the condition of 100 °C maintained 2 hours.

Table 1. Percentage of [0] Specimens' Fiber Proportion in Tensile Test

	J0	J90	G0	G90
0°	/	14.8	11.6	5.2
90°	14.8	/	5.2	11.6
0°	/	15	11.6	5.1
90°	15	/	5.1	11.6

Table 2. Percentage of [0/90/0] Specimens' Fiber Proportion in Tensile and Bending Test

	J0	J90	G0	G90
0°	5.9	11.8	10.7	8.3
90°	11.8	5.9	8.3	10.7
0°	6.1	12.2	11	8.5
90°	12.2	6.1	8.5	11

Fig. 2. Specimens of Jute-Glass hybrid fabric composites for tensile testing and their size

Fig. 3. One ply Jute-Glass hybrid fabric composites for bending testing

In table 1 and table 2, the percentage of jute and glass in composites is showed.

2.3 Tensile test

Tensile test were performed by using an Instron universal testing machine under a speed of 1 mm/min. Additionally, strain gage (KYOWA KFG-10-120-C1-11) was used to measure the strain during testing process. The camera system was employed to record the damage process of those specimens. According to the time, the camera speed was 30 frames per second. Different damage states can be obtained from the video. The tensile test specimens (including one ply composites in 0°, 45°, 90° and three plies composites in 0°, 90°) and their size is shown in Figure 2.

2.4 Bending test

3-point bending was conducted on [0/90/0] in 0 degree and 90 degree specimens. The machine used here is the same as the one used in tensile test, which was controlled by speed of 1 mm/min. The span distance is 40 mm. The bending test specimens and their size were shown in figure 3.

2.5 SEM

After tensile test, specimens with different fracture surface were gotten. The fracture surface of specimens were cut down at about 10mm high. The pieces were then use FINE COAT ION SPUTTER JFC-1100E to coat a surface of platinum before observing under SEM.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Tensile test

Camera System

The damage process of [0/90/0] specimens was recorded by camera system. Five characteristic photos were taken from the video for each specimen of type A 0 degree, type A 90 degree, type B 0 degree and type B 90 degree specimen.

In figure 4, the 1st photo shows the original condition of specimen. The 2nd photo shows the initial damage of specimen in the fiber perpendicular to loading direction. The 3rd photo shows the crack generated along loading direction. After that the loading increased slowly obviously until to the maximum load state in the 4 the photo. The last photo shows the failure specimen.

The main difference of damage characteristics between 0 degree specimen and 90 degree specimen in type A was different level of delamination. Comparing the specimen of (a) 4 and (b) 4, it is easy

(a) Damage Process of type A 0 degree specimen

(b) Damage Process of type A 90 degree specimen

(c) Damage Process of type B 0 degree specimen

(d) Damage Process of type B 90 degree specimen

Fig. 4. Damage Process of Type A and Type B Specimens in [0/90/0]

to find out that (a) 4 specimen is stratified, while (b) 4 specimen is not so evident. Compare the specimen of (a) 5 and (b) 5, type A 0 degree specimen is seriously damaged all through the specimen, while type A 90 degree specimen is not damaged so seriously. It is mainly because the jute fiber is concentrated in 90 degree.

The damage of type B 0 degree specimen is similar to the damage of type A 0 degree specimen, the initial damage happened between glass fiber and matrix vertical to load direction. The 4th photo of (a) and (c) shows that the stratification happened all through the specimens, and the specimen is seriously damaged compare to 90 degree specimen. The damage of type V 90 degree specimen is concentrated compare to type B 0 degree specimen.

Fig. 5. Load-Displacement Curve of One Ply

The load-displacement curve of one ply specimens is shown in figure 5, including one ply 0°, 45°, 90° in both type A and B. It can be found out that one ply

45 degree specimens can suffer only a low load before their fracture, but had the longest elongation compare to 0 degree and 90 degree specimens. Type A 0 degree specimen can suffer a stronger load before its fracture than type B 0 degree specimen does, while type B 0 degree specimen can suffer a longer elongation than type A 0 degree specimen does before fracture. Type B 90 degree specimen can suffer a larger load and a longer elongation before fracture than type A 90 degree specimen does. Regarding the type A and type B, it can be found out that for 0, 45 or 90 degree specimens, type B can suffer more elongation before fracture.

Fig. 6. Load-Displacement Curve In Three Plies

The load-displacement curve of three plies specimens is shown in figure 6, including three plies 0 degree and 90 degree in both type A and type B. It can be found out that in the structure of 0 degree, the specimen of type A suffered more elongation and load than the specimen of type B did. While in the structure of 90 degree, the specimen of type B performed better in elongation and load than type A did. It is obvious that the specimen in 0 degree can suffer more elongation and load than 90 degree specimen does in type A, while it was complicated in type B. The 90 degree specimen was stretched longer in smaller load than 0 degree specimen in type B did.

(a) Stress-Displacement Curve of [0]

(b) Stress-Displacement Curve of [0/90/0]

Fig. 7. Stress-Displacement Curve of [0] and [0/90/0]

Comparing the load-displacement curve in figure 5 and figure 6, it's obvious that three plies specimens can suffer more load before their fracture. However, it's still hard to say 3 layers specimens have better properties before analyzing their stress-displacement curve, cause the content of fiber was tripled. In figure 7, the stress-displacement curve of specimens in [0] and [0/90/0] is shown. Comparing (a) and (b) stress-displacement curve, the tensile stress of [0/90/0] specimens was higher than that of [0] specimens in both 0 and 90 degree, although it is not too much.

Fig. 8. [0/90/0] specimens after tensile test

In figure 8, the [0/90/0] specimens after the tensile test are shown. The layers of type B 0 degree specimen after tensile test were almost separated, which might be the reason why its strength is a little bit lower than that in [0] specimen. The layers of type B 90 degree specimen after tensile test were also separated, but still with some part unseparated, which might be the reason why its strength was higher than that in [0] specimen.

(a) Tensile Strength of [0]

(b) Tensile Strength of [0/90/0]

Fig. 9. Tensile Strength in [0] and [0/90/0]

Figure 9 shows the tensile strength in tensile test. The deviation is also showed in this bar chart. The tensile strength of 0 degree in [0] and [0/90/0] are almost the same in type A. The tensile strength of 90 degree specimen of [0/90/0] is significantly greater than that of [0] specimen in type A. However, the tensile strength of 90 degree in type A of [0/90/0] is a little lower than the strength of type A of [0]. This might be resulted by that the layer of 0 degree in [0/90/0] 90 degree suffered almost all the tensile load during this experiment.

In one ply specimens of type B, the tensile strength of 0 degree specimen is similar to that of 90 degree specimen. This might means that in type B structure, jute fiber can to some extend replace glass fiber with only little influence on the tensile property. After [0/90/0] tensile test on type B specimens, it is found that the tensile strength of 0 degree and 90 degree specimen is still similar. This experiment confirmed the result that in type B structure, jute can replace glass fiber with only little influence on tensile property.

SEM

The fracture surface of 90 degree one ply specimens after tensile test in type A and type B were observed through SEM, and several pictures were taken.

Comparing the high magnificant photos in figure 10, there are obvious differences in jute fiber (bundle) and glass fiber (bundle). Many jute fibers in type A were pulled out during the tensile test, while jute fibers in type B were fractured almost at the same flat as resin. Jute fiber bundles are also in disarray on fracture surface of type A specimen. It can be found out from those photos that the force acted on the interface and resin on specimen of type A, and the force concerntrately acted on the jute fiber (bundle) on specimen of type B.

The conditions about glass fibers are similar in those photos. They were pulled out and then broke. However, the glass fibers are in obvious different length on specimen of type A, while it is not so evident on specimen of type B. Besides, there are more resins left on glass fibers of type A specimen compare to glass fibers of type B specimen.

Considering that the properties of type B specimen perform better than that of type A specimen do in 90 degree, different method of jute fibers' fracture might be the main reason.

3.2 Bending test

Fig. 11. Load-Displacement Curve of type A and type B specimens in three plies

The Load-Displacement curve of bending test is shown in figure 11. Three plies of 0 degree and 90 degree in type A and type B were tested in bending test. From the load-displacement curve, it is indicated that 0 degree specimen in type A performed shorter deflection with the same load compare to the other specimens at the beginning. However, 90 degree specimen in type B suffered the strongest load before its fracture.

A STUDY ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTY OF GLASS/JUTE
INTER-LAMINATE HYBRID FABRIC COMPOSITE

Type A

Type B

Fig. 10. fracture surface of one layer specimen in type A and type B

Fig. 12. Stress-Displacement Curve of bending test

Considering the composites were in three plies and in 3 mm, the stress-deflection curve in figure 12 is also introduced here. The strength of type B 0 degree specimen is almost the same as that of type A 0 degree and 90 degree specimens.

Fig. 13 [0/90/0] specimens after bending test

Figure 13 shows the photos of specimens taken after bending test.

Fig. 13. Bending Strength of [0/90/0]

In order to compare the strength of these specimens, figure 13 is quoted. The bending strength is in the order of 90 degree type B specimen, 0 degree type A specimen, 0 degree type A specimen and 90 degree type B specimen. The bending strength of

type A 0 degree specimen and 90 degree specimen are similar, which indicates that glass fiber can be replaced by jute fiber in type A structure with only a little influence on bending strength.

4 Conclusion

Two type of jute-glass hybrid composite were evaluated by tensile test and bending test in one ply and three plies. load-displacement curve, stress-displacement curve and strength bar chart were quoted in this research for a better analysis. SEM was also used to observe the details of fracture surface of the specimens.

The follow points were concluded from this study:

1. According to tensile test results of [0] and [0/90/0] specimens, it indicates that glass fiber can be replaced by jute fiber with only a little influence on tensile strength in type B structure.
1. According to the observation by SEM in tensile test, it indicates that the force acted on the interface and resin on type A specimen, and the force concerntrately acted on the jute fiber (bundle).
2. According to bending test results of [0/90/0] specimens, it indicates that glass fiber can be replaced by jute fiber with only a little influence on bending strength in type A structure.

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